

LEADERSHIP AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP ADVANCEMENT: A PANACEA TO NATIONAL SECURITY, PEACE AND DEVELOPMENT.

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ABSTRACT

The paper focuses on leadership and entrepreneurship advancement as it relates to national security, peace, and development. It aimed at assessing the role entrepreneurship play in curbing social vices as it helps in job creation and how leaders can leverage it to develop the nation at all levels of governance. It also took a swipe on how organizations can leverage intrapreneurship to create a synergy that works instead of creating a breeding ground for unhealthy competitions. Sources of data for the paper were basically secondary from textbooks and websites. One of the recommendations made was the inclusion of government in the private sector through tax unification and support.

Keywords: *Leadership, Entrepreneurship, Intrapreneurship, Advancement, National development, Peace, Security.*

INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian narrative in recent times has been one that centers on continual insecurity, elusive peace brokering between government and deviant groups, kidnapping, highway banditry, amongst others. As a matter of fact, the government at all levels seems to have lost grip on handling the situation as security agencies are obviously overwhelmed.

One of the pointers to this kind of situation is basically unemployment. No matter how we try to shift the blame to other factors such as illiteracy, poor moral upbringing, and corruption, the fact remains that it is not a good time in Nigeria.

The trend, if allowed to escalate further, could threaten the unity of the nation and lead to the chaos which could eventually lead to civil war hence the need for something to be done and very fast too.

According to Oludele (2015), internal aggression is at an all-time high in Nigeria and the inability of any nation to tackle insecurity could spell doom in the long run.

The above assertion leads us to the term ‘national security’ which is one of the key functions of any government, i.e, securing the lives and properties of its citizenry.

A school of thought over the years has established that one of the ways to tackle insecurity is through job creation whereby the youth will be engaged and crime rate will further be minimized, and this could best be achieved through entrepreneurship. Mba (2014) puts it that ‘entrepreneurship is commonly considered as the engine room of economic growth and equitable development in developing economies. He stated further that it is labour intensive, capital saving, and capable of helping create most of the one billion new jobs the world will need by the end of the century.

As much entrepreneurship is one of the best ways of tackling insecurity and unemployment, it is imperative to also note that entrepreneurship can be taken a step further to have what is known as intrapreneurship. Intrapreneurship targets the embedded creativity and innovativeness of employees which include personal growth, development and management, orientation to punctuality, motivation, ability, and experience to collect resources and risk-taking. Oktem et al., (2003).

In a layman’s words, intrapreneurship will be referred to as the act of an entrepreneur working with another entrepreneur to improve a firm. Here, it goes beyond the salary earned but the synergy to create better service delivery to clients. According to P. E. C. Nwauba (2008), Intrapreneurship is a business within an existing business.

This paper takes an overview of the role of leadership in entrepreneurship advancement, considering it as a panacea to national security, peace, and development. It aims at exposing ways the government and entrepreneurs could leverage and maximize the power of synergy to bring about security, peace, and development.

ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND INTRAPRENEURSHIP: AN OVERVIEW

According to Elijah (2001), Entrepreneurship is the act of coming up with a business idea (original or borrowed), establishing it while building and nurturing it to generate a profit.

One of the major benefits of entrepreneurship is job creation and our society is basically in dire need of them (jobs) as it stands.

Intrapreneurship on the other hand is a build-up on entrepreneurship and its focus is on creating entrepreneurship within entrepreneurship. It takes out the idea of competitiveness and focuses more on synergy (a combination of idea forces).

Intrapreneurship helps ideas that would have lain fallow to be given life. Here, entrepreneurs that are engaged in the corporate sector bring forth their ideas to the management of their current place of employment; the ideas are analyzed and if viable, are adopted.

This implies that the hitherto employee becomes a part-owner of the firm and reaps more in terms of financial benefit coupled with the aura that goes with having a sense of belonging.

According to Thomas (2018), the 21st-century entrepreneur is not faced with the challenge of competition but rather the challenge of who to partner with or not hence the need for organizations to source talents with ingenuity and the ability to make decisions where necessary.

Entrepreneurship, or more encompassing, intrapreneurship is the new face of wealth creation that is set to take over the global economy as countries like the USA, Japan, and China are already leveraging on it.

THE ROLE OF LEADERSHIP IN ENTREPRENEURIAL DEVELOPMENT

Leadership plays a pivotal role in the development of entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship. As a matter of fact, leadership is one of the major factors that help entrepreneurship grow.

Leadership has to do with decision-making, policies, and financial backing.

In order for intrapreneurship to grow, the leaders of industries have to grant the youth with innovativeness the opportunity to join the sector with their ideas. Not just granting them the opportunity but also supporting them with the required financing and policies.

As much as most people believe that policies that enable businesses to grow to lie with the government, it is important to also note that players in different industries also inform the decisions made by the government. It is an open secret that some top entrepreneurs in Nigeria that have links with those in power have a way of lobbying government decisions on the monopoly of products and services. This affects the opportunities that would have to abound to young entrepreneurs in that sector that have been monopolized.

Leadership is supposed to allow for growth and succession but it seems key players are all about themselves and their cronies hence the inability of wealth to spread evenly. George (2014) posits that the middle-level stage in the strata of income earners is fast dying out as most people are either extremely rich or extremely poor. This can be concluded to be the inability of government policies to allow wealth to circulate.

CHALLENGES

Some of the challenges of leadership and entrepreneurship advancement in the Nigerian narrative are:

1. Policies: Governmental and executive policies are the bane of entrepreneurship development in Nigeria. For instance, the taxation system in Nigeria is not helping small

businesses grow. The problem of double and high taxation still thrives in Nigeria today. Most businesses have been shut down due to the inability to handle excessive taxes.

2. Fear: Most young entrepreneurs are scared of sharing their unique ideas with their bosses. There is this fear that their ideas could be stolen without any honorarium and taken to be the firm's (which the work) original idea. This makes them keep the ideas to themselves and probably die with it when opportunities to hone their skill never present themselves.

3. Financial Problems: Since most businesses in Nigeria are small-scale, there's a tendency that they might not be able to finance the ideas of their staff, especially when the ideas are capital intensive. This stands as a huge challenge which might make some staff to shelf their ideas.

4. Strong-willed Management: There are managements that are unwilling to change their status quo. The business philosophies of such firms are static and they are not ready to diversify to fact 21st-century realities. To such firms, staff ideas are never given a second thought, and pressing with such ideas could be considered insubordination. This makes staff keep their helpful ideas to themselves.

5. Inability to analyze break-even: Some business ideas might sound good and interesting to the ears but actually analyzing them to be viable might be difficult. The inability of some business ideas to break even at a given period could make firms not want to invest in them. This is where most business ideas from entrepreneurs pack up.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Having considered the concept of entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship, the role of leadership, and its challenges, here are some recommendations.

1. The Federal government and state governments should create an environment that facilitates ease of doing business. Taxation can be unified and reduced to encourage entrepreneurs, and in a wider scope, intrapreneurs.

2. Youth willing to go for intrapreneurship can handle fear by backing up their ideas legally. This could be done with the help of a lawyer so that their ideas could be personalized and authorization required before usage.
3. The Federal and state governments should make provision in form of loans and grants to support small businesses. This will further boost intrapreneurship.
4. Management of firms should relax their organizational policies/culture sometimes to allow for innovations especially when it's coming from staff members. Innovation could just be the key to drive the firm to the next height.
5. Business ideas that doesn't project a good break-even analysis is a deal breaker and should be revisited until that is achieved hence no finances should be committed.

CONCLUSION

Conclusively, good leadership with entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship are the future of Nigeria's economy if the government is determined to fight insecurity and unemployment to a standstill.

Supporting and enabling the private sector to thrive will definitely go a long way in developing the economy in the long run as many youth will be engaged hence less crime and secured nation for foreign investors.

Good leadership creates enabling atmosphere for entrepreneurship advancement (intrapreneurship) through good government policies and needed government assistance for job creation to foster national security, peace and development.

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